

CENTRAL ASIA AT THE CROSSROADS OF GLOBAL INTERESTS: THE CONTEMPORARY DIMENSION OF GEOPOLITICS

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Abstract. This article examines the growing geopolitical interest in Central Asia from major global and regional actors, including Russia, the United States, China, the European Union, Turkey, and the Arab states. The study focuses on the strategies and instruments these actors use to strengthen their influence in the region through economic, political, cultural, and security mechanisms. Special attention is given to the dynamics of external involvement and the competition for political and economic dominance in Central Asia. Based on the conducted analysis, the article formulates recommendations related to possible directions for strengthening the positions of Central Asian states amid increasing international competition.

Key words: Central Asia, international relations, geopolitics, political competition, strategic interests, transport corridors, natural resources, China, Russia, the United States, the European Union, Turkey, Arab states.

"Markaziy Osiyo global manfaatlar chorrahasida: geosiyosatning zamonaviy qirralari"

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Rossiya, AQSh, Xitoy, Yevropa Ittifoqi, Turkiya hamda Arab davlatlari kabi yirik global va mintaqaviy geosiyosiy subyektlarning Markaziy Osiyoga nisbatan ortib borayotgan qiziqishi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ushbu davlatlarning mintaqadagi ta'sirini kuchaytirish yo'lida qo'llayotgan strategiyalari hamda iqtisodiy, siyosiy, madaniy va xavfsizlik vositalari o'rganiladi. Xususan, tashqi kuchlarning mintaqaviy jarayonlarga aralashuvi dinamikasi va Markaziy Osiyoda siyosiy hamda iqtisodiy ustunlik uchun kechayotgan raqobatga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. O'tkazilgan tahlillar asosida maqolada xalqaro raqobatning kuchayib borayotgan sharoitida Markaziy Osiyo davlatlarining mavqeyini mustahkamlash bo'yicha ehtimoliy yo'nalishlarga oid tavsiyalar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Markaziy Osiyo, xalqaro munosabatlar, geosiyosat, siyosiy raqobat, strategik manfaatlar, transport yo'laklari, tabiiy resurslar, Xitoy, Rossiya, AQSh, Yevropa Ittifoqi, Turkiya, Arab davlatlari.

Introduction

At present, Central Asia occupies a special place in the system of international relations, serving as a geostrategic bridge between Europe and Asia. In the context of the rapid transformation of the global political architecture, interest in the region is significantly increasing. Global and regional actors seek to consolidate their influence by employing a variety of political, economic, and cultural instruments. At the same time, the Central Asian states are actively shaping their own foreign policy strategies, striving to maintain a balance between the interests of various external powers. The contemporary dimension of geopolitics in the region reflects not only the competition for access to resources and transport routes but also a broader rivalry over ideological, technological, and institutional influence. Studying these processes offers deeper insights into the dynamics of international relations in Central Asia.

Results and Discussion

The geopolitical significance of Central Asia is determined by its strategic location, substantial reserves of energy and natural resources, well-developed transport and transit potential, as well

as its proximity to zones of armed conflict that have a considerable impact on international security. These factors contribute to the continued and growing interest of major global and regional powers in the region. As a result, Central Asia has emerged as a strategic arena where the interests and strategies of external geopolitical actors, primarily Russia, the United States, China, the European Union, Turkey, the Arab states, and others intersect and compete.

Russia has traditionally maintained a strong presence in Central Asia, viewing the region as a key area of its strategic interests. Moscow's primary efforts are focused on ensuring regional security, strengthening economic ties, and promoting cultural and humanitarian cooperation. As one of the top three trading partners for most countries in the region, Russia plays a significant role in shaping a mutually dependent trade and economic environment, which contributes to the preservation of its influence across the Central Asian space¹. One of the key factors sustaining Russia's influence in Central Asia is labor migration. A significant number of Central Asian citizens find employment in the Russian Federation, and remittances sent by these migrant workers constitute a notable share of the gross domestic product of several countries in the region, including Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan², thereby reinforcing their economic dependence on Moscow. In order to maintain its positions, Russia actively promotes integration processes and military-political cooperation through organizations such as the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) and the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO). Russia's military presence in Central Asia is supported by a network of strategic facilities, including the 201st Military Base in Tajikistan, the Kant Air Base in Kyrgyzstan, the testing site on Lake Issyk-Kul, and the Sary-Shagan missile range in Kazakhstan³. These facilities enable Russia to maintain control over strategically important routes and preserve its influence in the field of defense. In addition, Russia is involved in the development of new logistical corridors and trade routes across Central Asia, aiming not only to strengthen its economic presence, but also to ensure the stability of its southern borders. For instance, Russia plays an active role in the advancement of international transport corridors such as the North–South Transport Corridor and initiatives connected to the Trans-Caspian route⁴. Thus, it can be concluded that Russia's policy in Central Asia is multi-vector in nature, combining economic, military-political, and humanitarian instruments to secure its long-term presence in the region.

China is actively strengthening its economic presence in Central Asia, using the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) as a key instrument for advancing infrastructure projects and expanding trade and economic ties⁵. Within this framework, Beijing is making large-scale investments in the construction of highways, railways, logistics hubs, ports, and energy infrastructure, all of which contribute to the accelerated economic development of the regional states. Notable examples include the China–Kazakhstan–Europe railway, the construction of the Khorgos International Centre for Border Cooperation, and the planned China–Kyrgyzstan railway, among others. One of the main mechanisms for enhancing China's influence remains the provision of

¹ Пятницкая М. В. Россия в Центральной Азии: механизмы влияния и ограничения // Вестник МГИМО. 2021. № 5 (80).

² Всемирный банк: миграция может стать инструментом развития в Центральной Азии [Электронный ресурс] // UzDaily.uz. 2025. 9 марта. Режим доступа: <https://www.uzdaily.uz/ru/vsemirnyi-bank-migratsiia-mozhet-stat-instrumentom-razvitiia-v-tsentralnoi-azii/> (Дата обращения: 15.03.2025).

³ Зверев Ю. Российские военные базы и объекты за рубежом: Казахстан, Таджикистан, Киргизия. 2017. [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <https://eurasia.expert/rossiyskie-voennye-bazy-i-obekty-za-rubezhom-asia/> (дата обращения: 20.02.2025).

⁴ Сипаро К.А. Роль России в развитии евразийских транспортных коридоров // Социальная и экономическая география. 2021. Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-rossii-v-razviti-ievraziyskih-transportnyh-koridorov> (Дата обращения: 10.04.2025).p

⁵ Belt and Road Portal. China's Belt and Road Initiative. Available at: <https://eng.yidaiyilu.gov.cn/p/0T4ND13J.html> (Accessed: 15 April 2025).

concessional loans⁶. China has extended substantial loans to Tajikistan to finance infrastructure projects, while Kyrgyzstan has received funding for the modernization of its energy sector, including the Bishkek Thermal Power Plant. Moreover, China views the countries of the region as strategic partners in ensuring stable energy supplies. Examples of such cooperation include the construction of the Kazakhstan–China oil pipeline⁷ and the Central Asia–China gas pipeline⁸, both of which have significantly strengthened energy interdependence between China and the Central Asian states. Thus, these countries are seen by Beijing as key partners in securing reliable energy flows and implementing large-scale infrastructure initiatives. At the same time, China does not pursue its strategy in the region through overt competition for dominance, but rather through deepening economic engagement. While formally adhering to a policy of non-interference in the domestic affairs of Central Asian countries, China's growing economic presence inevitably leads to an increase in its political influence.

The United States has shown a growing interest in strengthening its ties with the Central Asian states through the diplomatic platform C5+1, which brings together the five Central Asian countries and the United States. Washington is particularly interested in the region's vast natural resources, including oil, gas, and rare earth elements, which hold strategic value for high-tech industries and defense sectors. At present, the U.S. is seeking to reinforce its presence in the region, as reflected in the U.S. Strategy for Central Asia 2019–2025⁹. This strategy outlines efforts to support regional security, promote democracy, foster economic development, and establish stable trade and political relations. The primary long-term objective of the United States in Central Asia is to counterbalance the growing influence of Russia and China.

The European Union is actively strengthening its presence in Central Asia. At present, the EU is one of the most important trading partners for the countries of the region and is steadily expanding cooperation across a wide range of sectors, including energy, agriculture, environmental protection, climate change mitigation, as well as technology and innovation. The legal framework for this cooperation is established by two key documents: the EU Strategy for Central Asia¹⁰ and the Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreements (EPCAs) between the EU¹¹ and the countries of the region. These documents provide a foundation for the further expansion of political and economic engagement between Brussels and the Central Asian states. In addition, there are a number of other significant projects and initiatives between the European Union and Central Asia aimed at strengthening cooperation and addressing key regional challenges. These initiatives include the EU Action Plan on Human Rights and Democracy

⁶ World Bank (2019) Belt and Road economics: Opportunities and risks of transport corridors. Washington, DC: World Bank. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/regional-integration/publication/belt-and-road-economics-opportunities-and-risks-of-transport-corridors> (Accessed: 20 April 2025).

⁷ Казахстанско-Китайский трубопровод. Проект «Атасу – Алашанькоу» // Официальный сайт АО «Казахстанско-Китайский трубопровод». Режим доступа: <https://www.kcp.kz/projects/project1> (дата обращения: 20.04.2025).

⁸ Газопроводу «Центральная Азия – Китай» - 10 лет // NANGS. Режим доступа: <https://nangs.org/news/midstream/pipelines/gazoprovodu-tsentrallynaya-aziya-kitay-10-let> (дата обращения: 20.04.2025).

⁹ Посольство США в Узбекистане. Стратегия США для Центральной Азии на 2019–2025 годы [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <https://uz.usembassy.gov/ru/united-states-strategy-for-central-asia-2019-2025-advancing-sovereignty-and-economic-prosperity-ru/> (дата обращения: 21.02.2025).

¹⁰ Council of the EU. Central Asia: Council adopts a new EU strategy for the region // Press release. 2019. Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/delegations/en/the-new-eu-strategy-on-central-asia/product-details/20200331DPU25004>

¹¹ Европейская служба внешних связей (ЕСВС). ЕС строит прочные современные партнёрские отношения с Центральной Азией: обновлённая стратегия Европейского союза для региона. Информационный бюллетень. 2019. Режим доступа: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/factsheet_centralasia_2019_ru_digital_v1.pdf (дата обращения: 21.02.2025).

(2020), which is designed to support civil society, improve the status of women and children, and promote freedom of expression, including in the Central Asian countries¹². Another key project is the Water and Environment Cooperation Project (WECOOP, 2019), which focuses on sustainable water resource management, environmental protection, and the improvement of the ecological situation in the region through joint efforts by Central Asian states¹³. The EU's Global Gateway Initiative (2021) is aimed at mobilizing investments in infrastructure, digitalization, and sustainable development in partner countries, including those in Central Asia¹⁴. This initiative seeks to create efficient transport and digital corridors, as well as to promote the development of green technologies and energy efficiency. It should also be noted that cooperation in the field of natural resources and energy plays a particularly important role in the EU's strategy, as it is directly linked to strengthening Brussels' political influence in the region. In December 2022, the European Union and Kazakhstan signed a Memorandum of Understanding on strategic raw materials, which provides for the development of a partnership in the supply of critical resources such as lithium, uranium, rare earth elements, and other materials essential for high-tech and defense industries¹⁵. This agreement is aimed at diversifying the EU's supply chains and reducing its dependence on China. The European Union is also investing in the development of green energy projects in Central Asia, including solar and wind power initiatives in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. In the longer term, plans are being discussed for the export of green hydrogen from Kazakhstan to Europe, aligning with the objectives of the European Green Deal¹⁶. Through the implementation of these programs and projects, Brussels seeks to advance its strategic interests in Central Asia by offering the countries of the region alternative paths for development and integration into global processes.

Turkey regards Central Asia as a strategically important region for expanding its influence, relying on shared cultural, historical, and linguistic ties. Ankara's foreign policy strategy in the region is pursued both at the bilateral level and through multilateral institutional mechanisms. Turkey actively engages in the implementation of economic projects aimed at developing infrastructure, trade routes, and energy networks, while simultaneously strengthening political, economic, and cultural ties with the Central Asian states. Key roles in this process are played by organizations such as the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), within which the "Turkic World Vision 2040" is being implemented, the International Organization of Turkic Culture (TÜRKSOY), the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA), as well as other platforms for Turkic cooperation. Through these structures, Ankara seeks to promote the idea of a unified cultural and political space and to enhance the mutual integration of Turkic-speaking countries. Moreover, Turkey is significantly increasing its investment presence in Central Asia. Turkish investments cover key sectors of the economy: infrastructure, energy, agriculture, tourism, and small business. Joint projects are actively being implemented in road construction, airport modernization, energy infrastructure development, and agricultural

¹² The Diplomatic Service of the European Union. EU Annual Report on Human Rights and Democracy in the World 2020. Available at:

https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/eeas_annual_report_humanity_2021_web_0.pdf (Accessed: 22.02.2025).

¹³ WECOOP – Сотрудничество ЕС со странами Центральной Азии в области окружающей среды, климата и воды. [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <https://wecoop.eu/ru/about/> (дата обращения: 22.02.2025).

¹⁴ European Commission. Global Gateway [Electronic resource]. Available at:

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/stronger-europe-world/global-gateway_en (Accessed: 22.02.2025).

¹⁵ EU, Kazakhstan Strengthen Cooperation on Critical Raw Materials. The Astana Times, April 7, 2025. Available at: <https://astanatimes.com/2025/04/eu-kazakhstan-strengthen-cooperation-on-critical-raw-materials/>

¹⁶ Times of Central Asia. (2024). Kazakhstan, with China's Help, Plans to Export Green Energy to Europe. Available at: <https://timesca.com/kazakhstan-with-chinas-help-plans-to-export-green-energy-to-europe/> (Accessed: 25 April 2025).

production. For instance, in the field of infrastructure, Turkish companies such as MAPA Group and YDA Group are involved in the construction and reconstruction of highways, as well as the modernization of international airports in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. In the energy sector, Çalık Enerji is carrying out projects for the construction of power plants and transmission lines in Turkmenistan. In agriculture, Turkish agribusinesses are actively investing in the establishment of modern greenhouse complexes in southern regions of Kazakhstan, such as the Zhambyl and Turkistan regions¹⁷. Thus, Central Asia is seen by Turkey as a space for the implementation of a comprehensive strategy aimed at expanding its geopolitical and economic influence and strengthening its position on the international stage. Through the intensification of economic, cultural, and defense ties, Ankara seeks to establish itself as one of the key external actors in the region.

In recent decades, cooperation between Arab countries and Central Asia has been developing in response to new geopolitical and economic realities. Both regions possess significant strategic importance, and their interaction in areas such as economy, energy, security, culture, and education has been gaining increasing relevance. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in expanding economic cooperation between the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) and Central Asia. A notable example is the adoption of the Joint Action Plan for Strategic Dialogue and Cooperation between GCC member states and Central Asian countries for the period 2023–2027¹⁸. This plan envisions the development of joint investment projects, the promotion of mutual trade at the interstate level, and the establishment of working groups on cross-sectoral cooperation, food security, and energy security. Arab countries such as the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, and Kuwait possess substantial capital resources and advanced technologies, enabling them to invest in infrastructure projects in Central Asia¹⁹. These projects focus on the development of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power stations, as well as the construction of transport and road infrastructure. All of the above demonstrates the Arab countries' efforts to strengthen their economic presence through the development of cooperation and projects in Central Asia, which is of strategic importance in the context of global competition for resources and key trade routes.

Conclusion and recommendation

Thus, at present, we observe the following situation surrounding Central Asia: the region is becoming an arena of active competition among global and regional actors. Russia, the United States, China, the European Union, Turkey, the Arab states, and other participants in international relations are striving to consolidate their influence in the region by offering various programs, initiatives, and formats of cooperation in areas such as economy, infrastructure, energy, security, and culture.

Each of these actors pursues its own strategic interests, which increases the complexity of the international environment around Central Asia.

In this context, the countries of Central Asia face a key question: how should they shape their policies to preserve their sovereignty, strengthen internal resilience, and achieve sustainable development amid intensifying global competition? Addressing this challenge requires the countries of the region to pursue a purposeful and well-balanced strategy based on the following priorities:

¹⁷ Osipova, I. (2023). Turkey and Central Asia's Growing Partnership: Erdoğan's win marks continuity in Turkish economic and political engagement with the region. IWPR. Available at: <https://iwpr.net/global-voices/turkey-and-central-asias-growing-partnership> (Accessed: 20 April 2025).

¹⁸ Правительственный портал Республики Узбекистан. В Ташкенте состоялась вторая встреча министров иностранных дел Стратегического диалога «Центральная Азия – Совет сотрудничества арабских государств Залива» [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <https://gov.uz/ru/news/view/9578>.

¹⁹ Беленькая М., Константинов А. Центральная Азия нашла выход в Залив [Электронный ресурс]. Коммерсантъ. 2024. Режим доступа: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/6111603>

- First, it is essential to actively develop regional cooperation aimed at strengthening internal cohesion within Central Asia and coordinating efforts in the fields of security, economy, environment, and humanitarian interaction.
- Second, the countries of the region must focus on modernizing their economies and infrastructure, enhancing technological capabilities, transitioning to sustainable models of development, and supporting innovative industries.
- Third, a crucial priority should be institutional transformation: strengthening legal frameworks, improving the efficiency of governance, ensuring transparency, and fostering the development of civil society.
- Fourth, Central Asia must consistently strengthen its international agency by building balanced and mutually beneficial relations with external partners based on its own national interests and strategic priorities.

By adhering to such a course, the Central Asian states will not only preserve their independence in the face of growing external competition but also become a vital center of sustainable development and stability within the Central Asian space.

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